

IN THE COURSE OF GLOBALIZATION IN THE RANKS OF THE INTERNET INFORMATION SPACE

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Annotation: this article is written about the development of the internet and the history of its appearance on the sites in it.

Keywords: Arpanet, internet, web, Application, milnet, login;

The internet has become an integral part of the lives of millions of people in a short period of time, which quickly leads to the merger of civilizations that have brought the development of mankind to a new level, which has led to the exchange of information from different parts of the world. Looking at the history of the Internet, it can be seen that several political factors contributed to its emergence, since at a time when the breath of cold snap was shaking the world, the US government dreamed of creating a network that would contain all the documents that would survive even in a nuclear war, so the US Department of defense turned to RAND Corporation. Expert Paul Baran offers to transmit digital data using packets due to the fact that the technical transmission of a long-distance anal signal is difficult. The Pentagon is pleased with the ideas that they will turn to the AT&T telephone company to create such a network, but the company gives the conclusion that the scientist's ideas are nothing more than fiction. On October 4, 1957, the former Union for the first time in the universe flies the sun satellite of the Earth. It is reported that the US government, having concluded that the funds allocated by the Pentagon for scientific research are being spent in vain, will set up an ARPA agency for research on promising projects under the Ministry of defense, which will be tasked with creating a network that has no equal in the world. In 1967, Barley director Larry Roberts attended a scientific conference on the prospect of computer networks in England, where Wesley Clark's report on the network, consisting of patent communications carried out at the National Physics Laboratory of great Biritania, draws his attention. In December 1967, a network consisting of four nodes will be created, which will unite 4 US universities and will be called arpanet. In 1983, its military branches separated from ARPANET and operated as a separate MILNET network. As the new technology message begins to spread, scientists will understand its importance to the people of the scientific community, and the next improved system will begin to be used in 1972 by

connecting scientific centers at its university. On December 29, 1969, at 21.00 in the evening, the first communication signal is felt between the University of California in Los Angeles and the Sendafort Research Institute, located 640 kilometers from each other. Operator Charlie Cline tries to connect from Los Angeles on a computer located in Sendaphore. The output of each transmitted character on the monitor is confirmed by his colleague Duval over the phone. For the first time only three characters are transmitted these were just the first link of the LOGIN command word. After that, communication is interrupted but at 20.00, communication is restored in them and the word is transmitted completely, this date is officially recorded as the birth of the internet. In the Arpanet network, data transmission began to be carried out successfully. In 1971, a program for sending e-mail will be developed and will become popular in birzum. It is worth saying that research on the establishment of a global network was carried out not only in America, but also in other countries of the world. In 1965, David, a scientist at the National Laboratory of physics of England, offers to expand the experimental network, but his opinion is not supported by other scientists. After Wesley Clark's report in 1967, continuing his research, in 1973 he manages to create a communication packet network for a multidisciplinary laboratory. In 1976, the network had combined 12 computers and 75 terminal device bars. In 1970, networks in the UK and Narvegia would be added to the network via a trans-telephone cable, and from that year the network would gain international status. As a result of ARPA's support in 1903, the rules for the transmission of information between computer networks i.e. protocols are developed but the networks seen in other standards interfere with the successful operation of these protocols. This problem is solved by adopting a common protocol, and as a result of the transition to this protacol in all states on January 12, 1983, arpanet began to be called the internet. Since the first years of independence Uzbekistan has taken a worthy place in the world community, the mass introduction of modern information technologies in computer technology and their use in all spheres of public life create favorable conditions for the development of communication and Information Communication in order to expand the enjoyment of world information resources by more fully satisfying the needs of defines as one.

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